

The Independent Campus Learning Towards Industrial Revolution 5.0

Helvy Yunida¹, Awalludin Tjalla², Iva Sarifah³

^{1,2,3}Postgraduate Doctoral Program, State University of Jakarta, Department of Educational Research and Evaluation

ABSTRACT: The Independent Learning and Independent Campus are new curricula initiated by the Minister of Education and culture. This curriculum is in line with the character of young people in this digitalization era. Where today's young people have more interests and talents that are different from the past, therefore today is said to be the millennial era. Where today's young people do not want to be confined from the desire to be creative according to their interests, talents and potential according to their era. This idea is inseparable from the experience of the Minister of Education and culture abroad. He wants to develop the experience he got while abroad in Indonesia. Along with this digital era, Indonesia must be ready for the industrial revolution 5.0. With the implementation of independent learning and independent campuses, learners can fill their skills by participating in extracurricular activities in the form of courses, internships/work practices, Student Exchanges, Teaching Assistance in Education Units, Research/Research, Entrepreneurial Activities, Independent Studies/Projects and developing villages/ thematic real work lectures. Where this activity is carried out within the Study Program and outside the Study Program. The government hopes that after completing education, they can immediately prepare themselves to enter the world of work. So that college graduates are ready to use. Both enter the world of work and the world of entrepreneurship. So that there will be no more unemployment in Indonesia, because young people are ready to compete in the national and international arena. So that it can welcome the era of the industrial revolution 5.0.

KEYWORDS: Independence, learning, campus, Revolution, industry, 5.0

INTRODUCTION

According to the Ministry of Education and Culture (2020) that there are Principles of the Independent Learning Policy: Independent Campus including: Establishment of new study programs (Prodi) for State Universities (PTN) and Private Universities (PTS) with accreditation A and B, Re -Accreditation is automatic for all ranks, and is voluntary for Universities and Study Programs that are ready to advance to accreditation rankings, Examples and recommendations of partners who can cooperate with universities in the establishment of new study programs, Freedom for PTN Public Service Agencies (BLU) and Units Work (Satker) to become a Legal Entity PTN (BH), the right to take courses outside the study program and changes in the definition of Semester Credit Units (sks), student activities that can be carried out outside the home campus. (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2020). Education is a place that is very important and needed by every human being. With quality education, the younger generation will be able to prepare themselves for a higher era. The era of revolution 5.0 is ready to meet in front of us. We as a nation want to move forward to follow the era of globalization where every citizen is free to enter other countries to compete. Indonesia is prepared to adapt to this era. with the idea of merdeka to study at an independent campus, where the younger generation as learners, are prepared to fill their competencies according to their interests, talents and potential. Will make each individual happy to run. So that work, which should be an obligation for everyone, can be enjoyed with a sense of fun living it. When education has become a fashion, the younger generation will be ready to compete in the national and international arena. So that Indonesia is not left behind with other countries. Education is a medium to achieve prosperity for all mankind. Quality education also reflects an advanced and modern society. Education is the engine of culture. The habits of each age change in line with the changes obtained from the educational process itself. Education is able to produce creative, innovative things in treading every era of development. When a country wants to create a better life for all its people, education is an important element that must be prepared to fulfill these desires and ideals. In the context of Indonesia, education is also considered a very important and valuable thing. In fact, in the official constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, especially at the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution in the fourth paragraph, it is explicitly stated that the intellectual life of the nation is the responsibility of the State. (Mustaghfiroh, 2020)

The objective of the Independent Learning Campus policy is to encourage students to master various fields of science with their fields of expertise, so that they are ready to compete in the global world. This policy gives students the opportunity to choose the

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courses they will take based on their own wishes. The implementation of the Independent Learning Campus policy encourages the learning process in higher education to be more autonomous and flexible. Education always strives to create students who always make updates every time. Not only highly educated but able to become agents of change in small and large scope. The resulting changes and innovations are able to make a maximum contribution to the progress of a nation that has quality human resources. In writing this paper, the author uses qualitative research methods using a literature approach according to Kirk and Miller. (Deni Sopiandiah¹, dkk, 2022)

Independent Learning-Independent Campus is a policy of the Minister of Education and Culture which aims to encourage students to master various sciences to enter the world of work. The Independent Learning Policy-Independent Campus is in accordance with Permendikbud Number 3 of 2020 concerning National Higher Education Standards. The emergence of the policy of the Minister of Education and Culture in 2020 with the existence of Independent Learning and Independent Campuses (MBKM) provides a shift in views in the world of education, including education in universities. The concept of Independent Learning and Independent Campus means independence and independence for educational institutions, both in schools and universities. According to Nadiem Makarim, the concept of independent learning was chosen because it was inspired by the philosophy of K.H Dewantara with the essence of education meaning independence and independence. Freedom of learning is considered relevant and appropriate to be implemented in the current era of education democracy. This meaning of independence can be applied to educators in the classroom to be free to choose the right teaching method for their students and to be free to choose the best elements in the curriculum. The meaning of independence and freedom is education that emphasizes educational democracy. Merdeka Learning and Merdeka Campus are a form of reform carried out in learning from preschool education to higher education. This reform in independent learning is based on the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2020 Article 15 concerning Standards. (Susilawati, 2021) across scientific fields, able to process data science which one day will lead to an Indonesian perspective. Of course, in this case, universities must be adaptive to the changes in the concept of National Higher Education. (Baharuddin^{1*}, M. R. (2021)

In the fourth paragraph of the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, it is stated that one of the goals of the State of Indonesia is to educate the nation's life. Education as the development of thinking, acting and living competencies to become part of the world community Education 4.0 is a program to support the realization of intelligent education through improving and equitable quality education, expanding access and relevance to utilizing technology in realizing world-class education that produces collaboration, communication, critical thinking and skills skills. creative Changes in the world order globally need to be accompanied by changes in the skills needed. Universities must provide provisions to students by holding four core values, namely; adaptation, resilience, integrity and competence. In addition to the four core values, students must also have skills that must be mastered in order to be able to compete with graduates in national and international classes including; able to communicate, able to think critically and have creativity, receptive mind, have a sense of multicultural awareness, able to adapt, have the ability to work in preparing it globally. , (Aiman Faiz1, 2021)

Society 5.0 is also part of the fifth Science and Technology Plan initiated by the Japanese government as a society that has a future in realizing its ideals. Technological innovations that are growing rapidly are so influential in changing the social life of individuals. Freedom to Learn in the Era of Society 5.0 demands innovation that is so fast that it brings the current of rapid progress in the world of technology that has an impact on social life. Virtual and physical space no longer have boundaries, so that the lifestyle of the community will undergo such a significant transformation. The role of technology that greatly affects human life both in interacting and conducting transactions

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used is the literature review method. The literature review, according to Sugiyono (2012), is: "theoretical studies, references and other scientific literature related to the culture that developed in the social situation under study. Researchers collect reading sources, in the form of journals, books, web sites (Google Scholar), and others. This journal has a journal that is relatively the same topic. The goal is to compare opinions, both from research results, as well as from journals resulting from literature studies and other methods.

DISCUSSION

With globalization and reform, there has been a change in the educational paradigm. First, the paradigm of teaching-oriented educational process where the teacher is more of an information center, shifting to a learning-oriented educational process where students become the source (student center). Second, the paradigm of the traditional educational process which is oriented towards classical approaches and formats in the classroom, shifts to more flexible learning models, such as distance education. Third, the quality of education is a priority (meaning quality is international). Fourth, the increasing popularity of lifelong education and the melting of the boundaries between education in school and outside of school. Learner-centered learning does not mean handing over complete control of learning to students. Intervention is still needed and educators act as facilitators who try to help link the prior knowledge that students have with new information that they will learn. Provide opportunities for students to learn according to

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their respective ways and learning styles and encourage them to take responsibility for the learning process they do. In addition, educators also act as mentors, who seek to help students when they encounter difficulties in the process of constructing their knowledge and skills. (Elizabeth Simatupang¹), 2021)

Learning innovation 4.0 emphasizes the mastery of learning methods by educators, their application in the classroom, and their development in learning. Learning innovation utilizes all existing potential, including mastery of technology and its application in learning. Learning innovation 4.0 can be done in various ways. Educators certainly master the learning methods that have been applied so far. As for adopting and developing existing learning methods with a variety of their own creativity, this is the first step that can be taken in the context of learning 4.0. (Joenaity, 2019) The independent campus is an extension of the independent learning program which is still warm discussed in the field of education, it's just that the independent campus gives students the freedom for three semesters to seek learning experiences outside of their majors. Apart from that, this statement is a step towards improving the quality of education that was initiated by the Minister of Education, Nadiem Makarim. (Directorate General of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Culture, 2020). One thing that must be a concern in responding to the industrial revolution 4.0 is the speed of change from one period to the next. starting from the industrial revolution 1.0-2.0-3.0 about 100 years each. while from the industrial revolution 3.0 to 4.0 in less than 50 years. this shows that technology is really developing faster and faster. Learning rights are given to students for three semesters outside the study program, namely in the form of one semester of opportunity to take courses outside the study program and two semesters of carrying out learning activities outside the university. Activities outside of tertiary institutions can take the form of internships or work practices in industry or other workplaces, carrying out community service projects in villages, teaching in Education units, participating in student exchanges, conducting research, conducting entrepreneurial activities, conducting independent studies or projects, and participate in humanitarian programs. Nurhayani Siregar¹, R. S. (2020)

Independent Learning and Independent Campus are one of the policies of the Minister of Education and Culture Nadiem Makarim. There are two essential concepts in "Merdeka Belajar" and "Kampus Merdeka". First, the concept of independent learning implies the existence of freedom of thought. According to Nadiem Makarim, the essence of freedom of thought must be initiated by educators. This view should be seen as an effort to respect changes in learning in educational institutions, whether in primary, secondary or tertiary schools. Susilawati, N. (2021)

From the explanation of the policy concept of "Freedom of Learning" proclaimed by Mendkbud Nadiem Makarim mentioned above, there are parallels between the concept of "free learning" and the concept of education according to the progressive philosophy of John Dewey. The two concepts both emphasize the independence and flexibility of educational institutions in exploring maximally the abilities and potentials possessed by students who naturally have diverse abilities and potentials. If the two concepts are formulated, they both contain the same meaning, namely, students must be free and develop naturally; Direct experience is the best stimulus in learning; The teacher must be able to guide and be a good facilitator. Educational institutions must become educational laboratories for student change; Activities in educational institutions and at home must be cooperative. Education is also responsible for fostering students to be mature, brave, independent and self-employed. Thus the nuances of education should be strived to provide opportunities for students to always think independently and critically in finding their identity. In this context, the most important thing is not to give positive knowledge that is taken for granted to students, but how to teach students to have the power of reasoning. One of the efforts that can be done is to give independence to students to be directly involved in the learning process and transfer of knowledge. In this case, students are considered as the main subject, not just an object of an educational process. Mustaghfiroh, S. (2020)

To face the complex conditions of the times, it is necessary to renew the college curriculum so that students have the ability to solve problems with various scientific disciplines. The essence of the MB-KM student exchange program and general education is to facilitate students to be able to take knowledge from other scientific fields that they have never studied so that students can think flexibly and comprehensively. In addition to providing multidisciplinary or scientific transdisciplinary concepts, the student exchange program also provides provisions and character planting to recognize ethnicity, nation, culture, race and religion, thereby strengthening the essence of the value of national unity and integrity. Thus, cross-disciplinary science changes a new paradigm that every scientific field has the opportunity to be collaborated with other sciences through the MB-KM curriculum which is coherent with the general education curriculum. Aiman Faiz¹, P. (2021).

Implementation of the MBKM curriculum is of utmost importance because it involves partners to achieve learning outcomes in higher education. In its implementation, universities involve external parties in formulating curricula so that the results of their graduates can be accepted in the world of work. There are several agreed programs, namely: student exchanges, internships, work practices, teaching assistance in education units, research, research, humanitarian projects, entrepreneurial activities, independent studies/projects, village development/KKN. The existence of quality assurance in higher education is tasked with formulating quality policies and manuals, determining quality, carrying out monitoring and evaluation covering the principles of assessment, aspects of assessment and assessment procedures. With the MBKM curriculum, it is hoped that students who are currently studying in higher education must be prepared to become real learners who are skilled, flexible and tenacious (agile learners). The Independent Learning Policy - Independent Campus launched by the Minister of Education and Culture is a framework to prepare

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students to become strong scholars, relevant to the needs of the times, and ready to become leaders with a high national spirit. The objective of the Merdeka Learning - Merdeka Campus policy, the program "right to learn three semesters outside of the study program" is to improve the competence of graduates, both soft skills and hard skills, to be more prepared and relevant to the needs of the times, preparing graduates as future leaders of the nation's excellence. and personality. Experiential learning programs with flexible pathways are expected to facilitate students to develop their potential according to their passions and talents. (Deni Sopiansyah1, 2022).

Model Development of study program curriculum by adapting MBKM policy includes planning, learning process, assessment, and evaluation of learning. Services for fulfilling the period and study load as student learning rights, namely (1) Students are given the opportunity to take courses in their own study program, for a minimum of 84 credits. Which are mandatory core courses that will support the fulfillment of learning outcomes and profiles. Graduates of study programs (2) Students are given the opportunity to take courses in other study programs within the UNCP, a maximum of 20 credits according to the needs, interests and talents of students in the future, and (3) Students are given the opportunity to gain learning experiences in other universities and non-PT through Business Internships, Student Exchanges, Thematic Community Service Programs, Social Service and Final Projects. Maximum 40 credits. Implementation of the MBKM Curriculum through 5 program activities, namely the Student Exchange Program, Introduction to the School Environment through the Remote Area Movers Teacher Program, Business Internships, Thematic Community Service Program "Digital Literacy Education", and Social Service. Internal resources needed are UP for Introduction to School Environment, UP for student exchange, UP for Real Work Lectures, Academic Directorate, Directorate of Student Affairs, Directorate of Management Information Systems, and Advisor Lecturers. Meanwhile, the external resources needed are Civil Service Teachers, Business Mentors, Local Governments, and Social Institutions, Management Agency, and MBKM program partners. (Baharuddin1*, 2021)

The MBKM program also prompts the curriculum to open more elective courses for students including courses that can be taken in other programs or other universities. However, some courses must meet the equivalent learning outcomes set by the study program. There was a case in which one participant with literature specialization took an online course from Coursera. This course, although literally belongs to Arts and Humanities, can nevertheless be similar to any literary courses (Snyder) offered in the existing curriculum. Therefore, should students intend to take certain courses outside of their study program be it compulsory or elective, it is very essential to consult to the academic advisor or study program head in order to ensure its compliance with the MBKM Curriculum. It also worth-noting that students should earn a certificate, which is usually NOT free, upon completion of an online course so that it can be eligibly converted to credits in the transcript. Another elective course is Internship, which is designed for students so that they will be empowered in order to be prepared for the job market as well as proactive for job hunting. but it also presents some MBKM implementation challenges to tackle. First of all, the Ministry of Education and Culture has not provided the details and mechanism and how the internship is carried out, so the study program must produce guidelines and procedures for the students. And second, one of the emerging issues is the conversion and its grading system. When a student takes an internship course, he/she must complete a minimum of certain hours (100 for instance) per semester. Students are also responsible for arranging or adjusting their schedule so that the internship program will not collide with other lectures, so it turns out that having online learning would be reasonably beneficial to avoid the potential problem. Since its first launch in 2020, the curriculum has been implemented with some challenges like four-year educational planning, online courses grade conversion, internship credit conversion, building a partnership, and re-establishing academic and administration system. Almost all the challenges experienced during the application of MBKM program is related to administrative or paper work and few technical issues in the process. (Krishnapatria, 2021)

Such rapid innovation brings rapid progress in the world of technology that has an impact on social life. Virtual and physical space no longer have boundaries, so that the lifestyle of the community will undergo such a significant transformation. The role of technology that greatly affects human life both in interacting and conducting transactions. Society 5.0 or Society 5.0 is a concept from a section to integrate, balance the development of technological advances and social problems that combine the virtual and physical worlds. In addition, there are also those who interpret society 5.0 as a group of individuals who use technology in the era of industrial evolution 4.0 to solve problems in everyday life. Internet of Think and Artificial Intelligence have a full role in facing the era of society 5.0 with the aim of a group of individuals or society being able to enjoy a quality life. Marisa, M. (2021)

CONCLUSION

Freedom to study an independent campus is a new policy from the Minister of Education and Culture that can motivate students to develop their interests, talents and potential. With adaptations that have begun to be carried out in various fields of education, it is possible that the application of independent learning in independent campuses is immediately adopted by implementing it in schools and universities. Applications that are carried out according to good and correct procedures will trigger the competence of learners according to their field of interest. So that when you graduate from the bench of education, you are ready to use it in the world of work or the world of industry. When independent learning and independent campuses have increased the capability of the younger generation as the nation's successor in the millennium era in the industrial revolution 4.0. in the future it is possible to be able to

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meet the era of the industrial revolution 5.0. so that the preparation is more mature, so that the younger generation of Indonesia is not left behind and can be in line in quality with other developed countries.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aiman Faiz1, P. (2021). Koherensi Program Pertukaran Pelajar Kurikulum Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka dan General Education. *Edukatif : Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan* Volume 3 Nomor 3 Tahun 2021(Volume 3 Nomor 3 Tahun 2021), Halm 649 - 655. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31004/edukatif.v3i3.378> I
- 2) Baharuddin1*, M. R. (2021, April). Adaptasi Kurikulum Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka (Fokus: Model MBKM Program Studi). *Jurnal Studi Guru dan Pembelajaran*(Vol. 4, No. 1, Januari – April 2021). doi:<https://doi.org/10.30605/jsgp.4.1.2021.591>
- 3) Deni Sopiensyah1, S. M. (2022). Konsep dan Implementasi Kurikulum Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka. *Religion Education Sosial Laa Roiba Journal*. doi:10247476/reslaj.v4i1
- 4) Elizabeth Simatupang1), I. Y. (2021, April). Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka terhadap Perubahan Paradigma Pembelajaran pada Pendidikan Tinggi: Sebuah Tinjauan Literatur. *Jurnal Bisnis, Manajemen dan Ekonomi*(Vol. 2, No. 2, April 2021). Retrieved Oktober 3, 2022, from Email: elizabethsimatupang99@gmail.com
- 5) Fuadi1), T. M. (2020). KONSEP MERDEKA BELAJAR-KAMPUS MERDEKA (MBKM) : APLIKASINYA DALAM PENDIDIKAN BIOLOGI. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Biotik*. Retrieved Oktober 6, 2022
- 6) Kebudayaan, K. P. (2020, Januari 24). Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka. halaman 1-19. Retrieved Oktober 8, 2022
- 7) Krishnapatria, K. (2021, Juni). MERDEKA BELAJAR-KAMPUS MERDEKA (MBKM) CURRICULUM IN ENGLISH STUDIES PROGRAM: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES. *ELT in Focus*(Vol. 4(1) June 2021). doi:doi:10.35706/eltinf.v4i1.5276
- 8) Marisa, M. (2021, April). INOVASI KURIKULUM “MERDEKA BELAJAR” DI ERA SOCIETY 5.0. *Santhet: Jurnal Sejarah, Pendidikan Dan Humaniora*(Vol. 5, No.1). doi:DOI: 10.36526/js.v3i2.
- 9) Mustaghfiroh, S. (2020, Maret). Konsep “Merdeka Belajar” Perspektif Aliran Progresivisme. *Jurnal Studi Guru dan Pembelajaran*(Vol. 3, No. 1, March 2020). doi:<https://doi.org/10.30605/jsgp.3.1.2020.248>
- 10) Nurhayani Siregar1, R. S. (2020, Juli). KONSEP KAMPUS MERDEKA BELAJAR DI ERA REVOLUSI INDUSTRI 4.0. *Fitrah: Journal of Islamic Education*(Vol. 1 No. 1Juni 2020). Retrieved Oktobber 4, 2022, from <http://jurnal.staisumatera-medan.ac.id/index.php/fitrah>
- 11) Nurhayani Siregar1, R. S. (n.d.). KONSEP KAMPUS MERDEKA BELAJAR DI ERA REVOLUSI INDUSTRI 4.0 REVOLUSI INDUSTRI 4.0. P-ISSN : 2723-3847, .
- 12) Snyder. (n.d.). *Metode Penelitian* .
- 13) Susilawati, N. (2021, Maret). Merdeka Belajar dan Kampus Dalam Pandangan Filsafat Pendidikan Humanisme. *Jurnal Sikola, Jurnal Kajian Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*(VOL. 2 NO. 3 MARET 2021). doi:doi.org/10.24036/sikola.v2i3.108